

IPCC FAIR data approach

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The IPCC Working Group I Technical Support Unit (WGI TSU) and the IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC) Partners have implemented a new paradigm for data publication in the AR6 WGI report.

The IPCC, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, is the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change. It brings together scientists from all over the world to review the latest research and then make an expert assessment of the robustness of this knowledge.

WGI and FAIR principles:

The WGI of the IPCC recognizes the importance of open and transparent sharing of scientific data in the field of climate change research and for a robust and transparent IPCC assessment. By implementing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, WGI has ensured that much of their data and other digital resources are accessible to other scientists, researchers, practitioners, and policymakers around the world. These users are able to navigate between the resources through one-way and often two-way linking.

The DDC Partners have devoted resources to ensure that the data is well-organized, well-documented, and preserved for long-term use according to best practices for repositories. These best practices are described in the criteria of the Core Trust Seal, which is an integral part of the application process for a Regular Membership of the World Data System (WDS).

Challenges and lessons learned:

Several challenges related to new organizational needs and a lack of pre-existing tools across the workflow were addressed. These are discussed in the AR7 recommendations and ongoing initial work aiming at a more exhaustive and reliable data and software usage documentation in the upcoming AR7:

- Expectations for data management need to be provided to authors from the start as an integral part of the assessment process.
- Figure creation provenance information should be obtained from IPCC authors and should include all information required by the IPCC Data Guidelines. The Figure Manager serves as a platform for providing this information, which is used for data referencing and data traceability.
- A reference to information about figure creation should be part of the figure caption and figure pages to increase their transparency. The development is carried out together with the RDA Complex Citation WG.

References:

- IPCC (2023). TG-Data Recommendations for AR7 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10059282>
- Pirani et al. (2022). The implementation of FAIR data principles in the IPCC AR6 assessment process. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504469>
- Pirani et al. (2022). Experience in the Implementation of FAIR Data Principles in the WGI AR6 Assessment (Version 1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6992173>
- Stockhause et al. (2019). Data Distribution Centre Support for the IPCC Sixth Assessment. Data Science Journal, 18(1), p. 20. <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-020>

IPCC Links:

- IPCC <https://www.ipcc.ch/>
IPCC WGI AR6: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>
IPCC DDC: <https://www.ipcc-data.org>

